

KASB TANLASHGA YO'NALTIRISHNI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA O'QITISH METODIKASI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada kasb tanlashga yo'naltirishning pedagogik texnologiyalar asosida o'qitish metodikasi yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: texnologiya, maqsad, vazifa, nima uchun, klaster.

Аннотация. В данной статье описана методика обучения профориентации на основе педагогических технологий.

Ключевые слова: технология, цель, задача, зачем, кластер.

Abstract. This article describes the methodology for teaching career guidance based on pedagogical technologies.

Keywords: technology, goal, task, why, cluster.

Texnologiya fanini kasbga yo'naltirib o'qitish texnologiya o'qituvchisini kasbga tayyorlashning umumiy tizimidagi asosiy fanlardan biridir. U o'quvchilarga texnologiya o'qitish jarayonining asosiy qonuniyatlarini, metodlari va vositalarini, shuningdek texnologiyani boshqa fan asoslari bilan aloqadorlik xususiyatini o'rgatadi.

Asosiy **maqsadi** – bo'lg'usi texnologiya o'qituvchilarining kasbga tayyorgarligini shakllantirish va rivojlantirish hamda metodik ko'nikma va malakalarini hosil qilishdan iboratdir.

Texnologiya fanini kasbga yo'naltirib o'qitishining **vazifasi** - o'quvchilarni umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktab, akademik litsey, kasb-hunar maktablarining texnologiya fani bo'yicha o'quv dasturlari va ularning tarkibi bilan tanishtiribgina qolmay, ularni o'quvchilar, o'quvchilar ongiga singdirish va amaliyotda foydalanish metodlari, texnologiyalari bilan tanishtirishdir. Bunda har bir o'quvchi o'qituvchilik faoliyatida foydalanish zarur bo'lgan barcha yo'l-yo'riqlar, pedagogik faktlar, ayrim mavzularni darsda o'tish, o'quvchilarga o'rgatish, darsda ko'rsatma materiallar, texnik vositalar, test reytinglar va hokazolardan foydalanish metodlari bilan tanishadilar hamda amalda sinab ko'radilar.

Texnologiya o'qituvchisining o'quvchilarni mehnat tarbiyasi va kasbga yo'naltirish bo'yicha ish metodini aniqlovchi tamoyil bo'lib kasbiy tamoyil hisoblanadi. texnologiya o'qituvchisi o'z darslarida avvalambor o'z faniga o'quvchilarni qiziqтира olishi zarur, aks holda u hozirgi ishlab chiqarishning ilmiy asoslari haqida, novator va ijodkorlar haqida har qancha chiroyli so'zlab bersa ham o'quvchida mehnatga ijodiy munosabat shakllanmaydi.

Ta'lim muassasalarida ishlayotgan texnologiya o'qituvchilarining yana bir muhim vazifasi shundan iboratki, u o'z darslarida texnologiyani o'quvchilarning kelgusidagi mehnat faoliyatlariga qanchalik zarur ekanligini aniq misollar orqali ko'rsatib bera olishi va ularni tajribalar orqali namoyish etib berishi kerak bo'ladi. O'qituvchi shu yo'l bilan o'quvchilarni texnologiya faniga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshirish bilan birga o'z kasbiga muhabbat tuyg'usini ham uyg'ota oladi.

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